

GOALS AND TASKS OF FORMING PROFESSIONAL ETHICS SKILLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS

Bekberdiyeva Gulbahor Ortiqaliyevna

Teacher of Business and Science

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11408297>

It is an important task to educate students in higher educational institutions in the spirit of love for pedagogical activity and work. The main indicator of future teachers' success in this regard is the quality of lessons. Because during the course of the lesson, it will be possible to observe and evaluate the teacher's professional culture, personality, interaction with students, skills, interest in his profession, acquisition of knowledge.

In future teachers, he is a pedagogic level leader, he shows directions in teaching pedagogy and educates students.

Speaking about the problems of reforming the continuous education system, the 1st President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov said: "In order to ensure the living needs of teachers and educators, to raise the prestige of their profession, we encourage them to work hard. we must jump." He continued: "... it makes no sense to talk about the education of the next generation without solving it (this problem)".

The priority of future teachers' work is based on three "points":

- the first is the qualification, cultural and spiritual level of the teacher;
- the second is the moral responsibility of teachers for the pedagogical perfection of the learner;
- the third is material and social support, a teacher in preparing the next generation for harmonious development, growth, and gaining prestige the importance of labor through the training of qualified personnel role in economic growth.

In the national program of personnel training, certain requirements are set for the personality of the teacher, which generally form the model of a modern teacher. The following are the main requirements:

- to be able to teach;
- failure to educate;
- personal qualities;
- objective assessment and control of students' knowledge manage to do;

In turn, many important factors affect future teachers' ability to meet the above requirements in the formation of their professional qualifications:

- supporting the educational process and its environment;
- physical, mental and pedagogical training of the teacher;
- knowledge of professional information sources;
- deep knowledge of science, professional competence and talent;
- awareness of new pedagogical technologies;
- regular striving to improve one's work;
- good knowledge of the normative documents of the continuing education system;
- mastering computer technology;
- information base and resources

The success of education depends on the culture and spirituality of the teacher, his personal behavior and reputation, high level of patriotism and sense of duty. In order to form a holistic view of the world, high culture, spirituality and global thinking in students, the teacher should have extensive humanitarian and humanitarian training, as well as the ability to organize educational work.

The teacher's personal qualities are demandingness and fairness, honesty and benevolence, politeness and feeling of kindness. These qualities determine the reference (value) of the teacher for students.

Achieving objective assessment is closely related to the ability to teach and educate students' knowledge in a psychological and pedagogical sense. As for objective assessment tools, the teacher must know them and use them at an excellent level. This is the ability to manage rating control, develop and apply standardized tests, etc.

The state policy in the field of personnel training freely chooses professional training, has high professional knowledge, is capable of fulfilling socially important tasks with a deep sense of duty, creative perception of talent and goals, responsibility for the growing generation. means to prepare and raise a comprehensively developed person who understands his socio-pedagogical role in front of the society.

For this purpose, special emphasis is placed on forming optimistic social and personal motives for choosing this profession in future specialists - pedagogues. The motive is to encourage a person to perform activities related to the satisfaction of needs, to stimulate activity and to determine not only his orientation, but also his behavior, and it is caused by a number of external and internal conditions. In short, a motive is a conscious reason for choosing a type of behavior and behavior that fulfills a person's needs.

Objective qualities, interests and ideals that carry personal meaning can be the triggers of the motive. Change and growth will be characteristic of a person when he has too many tasks and new motivations for his activity. Motive is one of the reasons that determines a certain orientation of a person.

Factors capable of bringing a person to a highly active state are necessary. How to form social and personal motives for choosing the teaching profession in future teachers? First of all, it is necessary to use the following pedagogical technologies: in the past, for example,

- Narrating relevant passages from the works of well-known pedagogues in the Middle Ages and today;
- referring to the memories and stories of students expressing the motives that caused them to choose the teaching profession during their school years;
- state guarantees aimed at increasing the role and importance, prestige and status of the teaching profession in our country (based on relevant government documents and the "National Personnel Training Program");
- to explain the current social position of the teacher in the continuous education system of our republic;
- tell the story that the teaching profession is always and especially today prestigious (using articles from the pedagogical publications of the republic);
- revealing the professional and personal perspectives of pedagogical activity (studying in family education, improving professional qualifications, scientific growth, advancement in service);
- to convey to students that the teaching profession is a unique creative activity built on the basis of self-awareness and self-realization;
- conducting conversations with future teachers about the content of professional training and the acquisition of general, professional-pedagogical and special knowledge. (It also discusses the possibilities and perspectives of goal-oriented education, harmonious development of the individual in all aspects, formation and improvement of the pedagogical image;
- listening to stories and information about the actualization and socialization of professional and personal achievements in the conditions of a higher educational institution and pedagogical practice;
- to convince future teachers of personal, professional self-improvement (guided or independent), for this it is necessary to have professional and personal interest.

It is important to focus students' attention on the personal emotional-need aspect and social level in the formation of social and personal motivations

for choosing the pedagogic profession in future teachers. In this case, it is necessary to assume that these motives are gradually understood in the process of pedagogical preparation and absorbed into the minds of students during the activity, especially during pedagogical practice, and that the main criterion - the state of social-pedagogical activity needs self-evaluation. It is possible to imagine the motivational work conducted with future teachers, guiding them to pedagogical activities, based on the understanding of social and personal motives, in the form of a systematic plan.

The form and structural-content bases of the process of formation of social-personal motives for choosing a specialty among students-future teachers are developed taking into account the following:

- methodological tasks of modern education;
- requirements set for the personality of pedagogical staff in the national program;
- the personality of the subject of education, including youth psychology;
- theory of motivation, growth of motive;
- Acquaintance with successes in the field of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan;
- the current state of pedagogical staff training;
- psychology of motivational work with future teachers;
- the ability of students to define their own perspective by foreseeing the future;
- pedagogical technology of this process;
- factor of social activity;
- values-based approach and objective self-assessment;

The following are the main criteria of social and personal motives in choosing the pedagogic profession of future teachers:

- emotional approach to the motivation factor of future teachers;
- interest and need;
- awareness;
- diagnosing the results of one's own pedagogical training, anticipating the future;
- socialization of this motive in activities, including pedagogical activities;
- to evaluate the future teacher's realization of social and personal motivations in direct activities - outside the classroom, in the audience, in public work, in educational pedagogical practice.

It should be noted that in the formation of social and personal motivations for choosing a profession in the future teachers, interest takes precedence as the basis and necessary condition of the educational process and any activity. It is interest and motivation that motivates and directs the personality of future teachers to the educational process, organizes students' thinking and intellectual-creative activities, their professional future creation and social-pedagogical orientation, and activates.

However, before this, it is necessary to have an indication of the expected result (based on the goals and tasks of education) and a clear goal. In the formation of socio-personal motives of future teachers in this structural-content system, not only the chosen profession, its social-personal essence is sufficiently deep and understood, but also the goal of social values is meaningful.

Pupils rise to a state of high social activity. In addition, social education of the individual takes place. In this way, a socially active specialist who is strictly professionally oriented to the educational system, worthy of the name of teacher and who takes it as a professional pride is formed.

The socio-personal motivations of the future teachers' choice of profession are a very important factor in the system of training pedagogues, and they control the activity of tomorrow's specialist as an individual. The system of activation of future teachers for their chosen profession can be expressed as follows:

Table - 1.

Social and personal motivational activities of future teachers can be reflected in the following table:

Table – 2.

Social and personal motivation activities of future teachers		
Education	Community work outside the auditorium	During pedagogical practice
Making ends meet		
Evaluating future teachers' performance in accordance with the content of the "I" concept	Analysis and evaluation of future teachers by the teacher according to the main criterion - social activity, educational, extracurricular and pedagogical activities	

Modern times and technological development require the teacher to be creative, to be able to think freely about the important problems of science, to be able to convey the achievements of science to students, and finally to teach students to think creatively and do research.

Therefore, the teacher must acquire research skills first. The teacher collects, analyzes and draws conclusions based on scientific research. In the process of using science conclusions in his practical work, he acquires very important qualities necessary for a modern teacher.

Pedagogical experience is the sum of knowledge and skills acquired by a teacher in the course of educational work. This is the teacher's pedagogical skill, which is the primary factor in the development of the science of pedagogy.

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